

Supplementary Figure S3. Q-Q plots for all traits evaluated under control and drought stress conditions in 144 potato varieties. 1 to 12 refers to each of the 12 potato chromosomes, 0 are control markers that are not associated with any chromosome and 13 refers to the chloroplast.